

A Study on Reading Comprehension Ability in Bengali among Standard IX Students of North 24 Parganas, West Bengal : Related to Location of School

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ABSTRACT : Reading comprehension is the procedure of making meaning from text. The goal, therefore, is to gain an overall understanding of what is described in the text rather than to get meaning from isolated words or sentences. The objectives of the study were to compare the reading comprehension ability between rural and urban students through two types of tests. Tests were administered on 520 samples from 10 schools (rural-5, urban-5) of North 24 Pgs. The collected data were analyzed by Mann-Whitney Test. The major findings were observed that in all section urban students scored better than rural students. The probable causes behind this type of result were discussed.

Keywords : Reading comprehension, ability

Introduction

Reading comprehension is a highly interactive process that takes place between a reader and a text. Individual readers will carry variable levels of skills and experiences to these interactions. These include language skills, cognitive resources and world knowledge. Any

act of reading occurs within a particular socio-cultural and emotional context. This consists of essentials such as the child's home culture, their previous experiences of reading and being read to, their expectations that reading should carry meaning, their motivation, their view of themselves as a reader, the intention for reading

the text, the cultural value placed on reading and the reading environments the reader experiences. While the motive of this document is to concentrate on looking closely at the development of comprehension skills, this broader context and its influences should be stand in mind.

Objectives

1. To study and compare the reading comprehension ability among the students of: Rural Schools & Urban Schools (Bengali Medium).
2. To assess the reading comprehension ability of the sample students through
 - a. Comprehension Test (M. C. Q. Test)
 - b. Cloze Test
3. To compare the performance of the total group in M. C. Q. test and Cloze test.

Hypothesis

For this study following null hypotheses were framed

- i. There will be no significant difference between the students of Rural Schools and Urban Schools in their performance in M.C.Q. Test in Bengali.
- ii. There will be no significant difference between the students of Rural Schools and Urban Schools in their performance in Cloze Test in Bengali.
- iii. There will be no significant difference in total reading comprehension ability between the students of Rural Schools and Urban Schools.

Sample and sampling procedure

The total schools of North 24 Parganas (Secondary & Higher Secondary) were stratified on the basis of locality (Urban & Rural). Thereafter from the stratum total ten schools were taken purposively. After fixing the schools the researcher has taken all the standard IX students presented on that day as the sample of the present study. Thus the sample size got a figure of 520. The nature of the final sample of the study is detailed bellow.

Table : 1 Locality wise sample distribution list

Locality	Sample Schools	Sample Students
Urban	5	249
Rural	5	271

Preparing of Research Tools

1. M.C.Q. Test

The researcher selected a short story of reputed Bengali Author for the test. The test was constructed by a passage of 176 words and 10 multiple choice questions. After that he justified from three Bengali Language teachers of different schools as the test may applicable or not for the standard IX students.

2. Cloze Test

A standard cloze test is a passage with blanks of standard length replacing certain deleted words which students are required to complete by filling in correct words or their equivalents. In traditional 'cloze test', every fifth word is removed from a 250-500 word reading passage. Usually, no word is deleted either in the first or the last sentence of the passage. Students are required to supply either the original word of

the author or an appropriate equivalent word in the blank space (Helfeldt et al, 1986:216).

The researcher selected a passage of reputed Bengali Author for the test. After that he justified from three Bengali Language teachers of different schools as the passage may applicable or not for the standard IX students. Then the researcher made the test with the help of his guide following the procedure of a standard cloze test, which was constructed by a passage of 477 words where 100 words were deleted (every fifth word) except in the first and last sentences.

Table : 2 Descriptive statistics of data

		Statistics	Std. Error
M.C.Q. Test	Mean	5.93	.076
	Median	6.00	
	Variance	2.992	
	Std. Deviation	1.730	
	Skewness	-.093	.107
	Kurtosis	-.570	.214
Cloze Test	Mean	45.0337	.89896
	Median	45.000	
	Variance	420.225	
	Std. Deviation	20.49938	
	Skewness	.255	.107
	Kurtosis	-.630	.214
Total Reading Ability	Mean	50.9663	.92765
	Median	50.000	
	Variance	447.478	
	Std. Deviation	21.15368	
	Skewness	.250	.107
	Kurtosis	-.639	.214

Data Collection

After preparing the tools, the researcher went to the selected schools and concern with the Headmaster or Headmistress. With their permission and help the tests (M.C.Q. Test & Cloze Test) were administered on all the 520 subjects of different schools. For the M.C.Q. Test they had given only 15 minutes and for the Cloze Test 50 minutes had given to the subjects. The data were collected and organized in tabular form for analysis.

Table : 3 M.C.Q. Test - Cloze Test - Total reading ability

Location of School		M.C.Q. Test	Cloze Test	Total reading ability
Rural	Mean	5.47	35.0821	40.5507
	Std. Deviation	1.589	15.64355	15.94739
	N	271	271	271
Urban	Mean	6.44	55.8645	62.3022
	Std. Deviation	1.738	19.67219	20.29804
	N	249	249	249
Total	Mean	5.93	45.0337	50.9663
	Std. Deviation	1.730	20.49938	21.15368
	N	520	520	520

Analysis and Interpretation

The collected data were analyzed following appropriate statistical procedures as given below:

Testing of Null Hypotheses

Table : 4 Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
M.C.Q. Test	520	5.93	1.730	2	10
Cloze Test	520	45.0337	20.49938	1.00	97.50
Total Reading Ability	520	50.9663	21.15368	8.00	104.50

Table : 5 Comparison of Scores

	Location of School	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
M.C.Q. Test	Rural	271	218.27	59150.00
	Urban	249	306.47	76310.00
Cloze Test	Rural	271	189.47	51346.50
	Urban	249	337.81	84113.50
Total Reading Ability	Rural	271	188.02	51346.50
	Urban	249	339.38	84506.00

Interpretation

H₀1: *There will be no significant difference between the students of Rural Schools and Urban Schools in their performance in M.C.Q. Test in Bengali.*

Table : 6 Test Statistics of M.C.Q. Test

	M.C.Q. Test
Mann-Whitney U	22294.000
Wilcoxon W	59150.000
Z	-6.782
Asymp.Sig.(2tailed)	.000

For comparing the M.C.Q. Test performance between rural students and urban students, the Mann-Whitney test was conducted. The

calculated 'U' value found as 22294.00 and 'Z' = - 6.782, the 'P' value is .000 (P < 0.05). Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It can be concluded that in case of performance in M.C.Q. Test, rural students and urban students differ significantly.

H₀2: *There will be no significant difference between the students of Rural Schools and Urban Schools in their performance in Cloze Test in Bengali.*

Table : 7 Test Statistics of Cloze Test

	Cloze Test :
Mann-Whitney U	14490.500
Wilcoxon W	51346.500
Z	-11.247
Asymp.Sig.(2tailed)	.000

For comparing the Cloze Test performance between rural students and urban students, the Mann-Whitney test was conducted. The calculated 'U' value found as 14490.50 and 'Z' = -11.247, the 'P' value is .000 (P < 0.05). Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It can be concluded that in case of performance in Cloze Test, rural students and urban students differ significantly.

H₀3: *There will be no significance difference in total reading comprehension ability between the students of Rural Schools and Urban Schools.*

Table : 8 Test Statistics of Total Reading Ability

	Total reading ability
Mann-Whitney U	14098.000
Wilcoxon W	50954.000
Z	-11.476
Asymp.Sig.(2tailed)	.000

For comparing the performance in reading comprehension test (both M.C.Q. Test & Cloze Test) between rural and urban students, the Mann-Whitney test was conducted. The calculated 'U' value found as 14098.00 and 'Z' = -11.476, the 'P' value is .000 ($P > 0.05$). Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It can be concluded that in case of performance in reading comprehension test (both M.C.Q. Test & Cloze Test) rural and urban students differ significantly.

Findings

- i. Urban students are much better than the rural students in M.C.Q. Test performance in reading comprehension.
- ii. Urban students are much better than the rural students in *Cloze Test* performance of reading comprehension ability in Bengali language.
- iii. Urban students are much better than the rural students in total reading comprehension ability on the basis of both type of test (M.C.Q. Test & *Cloze Test*) in Bengali language.

Discussion

Statistical analysis shows that locality of school influences the attainment in Reading comprehension. Comprehension is the end of all reading activity. Students from urban schools score better than rural schools in the skill of

Reading comprehension in Bengali. The sub-skill of Reading the lines - Understanding the context is influenced by the Locality of school. This skill helps in identifying the information and getting the literal meaning of the text. Reading between the lines an interpretative level of comprehension and its sub-skill arriving at unsaid facts are influenced by the Locality of school, estimating the worth of the details given is the reader's judgment, based on his own experiences. Judging characters and ideas is the skill where the reader infers the traits of the character from contextual clues. Students of urban schools are better than the students of other categories in the above sub-skills of Reading beyond the lines, and this ability in turn helps the students in Semi-urban schools to score better in the dimension Reading beyond the lines, a critical level reading. This may be the reason why a marked difference is noted in favor of urban students in the skills of Reading comprehension in Bengali. The present study also states that students of urban schools score better than the rural students. Some sociological reasons may be given for this difference. Urban locality may have large percentage of higher and higher- middle class population trying to come up in life through education. Therefore they may consider education much important. As a result teachers in urban schools may be forced to work harder to make the students learn better. Moreover, reading activity may be predominant in the higher and higher- middle class families due to the availability of newspapers, magazines and periodicals. Thus Urban students may be better equipped than rural students in the basic skills of reading so as to manifest a higher level of Reading comprehension in Bengali.

Locality of school influences Reading readiness and its components Perceiving information, Perceiving the concept Readiness to guess the meaning and Reading graphs and tables Many of the studies on Reading readiness have investigated it in relation to locality as Rural and Urban. Several studies as in the case of Patel (1983) have brought forth the finding that urban groups are better than the rural ones. Unlike these studies in the present investigation the investigator has studied the locality in terms of Rural and Urban. Because of this a detailed understanding of the groups which stand distinct due to economic, educational and social conditions is made possible. A large percentage of urban localities may be in white collar or blue collar jobs with higher academic or technical qualifications. Therefore for their children there may be a better exposure to reading and reading related activities. It is confirmed by the higher level achievement of urban students in the skills of Reading comprehension. Moreover it also reveals the fact that the higher economic and higher Social status of the Urban placed pupils and the lower economic and lower Social status of the Rural oriented pupils are of no use for the respective pupils with regard to their development of Reading comprehension. Likewise Locality of school seems to influence the Reading attitude of standard IX students. The general criticism is that students from rural schools are poor in Bengali language comprehension.

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Conclusion

The study shows the higher level achievement of urban students over rural students in the skill of reading. Naturally, therefore one may presuppose the presence of positive attitude towards Bengali. In the case of rural students their attitude towards reading is positive unlike the students of other categories. But in spite of this they are of the moderate level as others in Reading comprehension. It may be cause of the pull of certain other intellectual, social, emotional and linguistic factors found in them.

References

- Shermila, A. Joycilin, *A Study Of Skills Of Reading Comprehension In English Developed By Students Of Standard IX In The Schools In Tuticorin District*, Phd. Thesis, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli.
- Sharma, I. S. 1993, *On Language Comprehensibility*, NCERT.
- Sharma, I. S. 1986, *A study of the Effect of Psycho-social Factors on the Comprehensibility of Language Used in Text books at Primary Stage*: NCERT (memo.) New Delhi.
- Sharma, I. S. 1985, *Towards a Model of Textbook Comprehensibility*, NCERT, New Delhi.
- Kaushik Sonika, 2008, *Reading For Meaning : A collection of writings on the process of reading*, NCERT.
- Kaul, Lokesh, 2012, *Methodology of Educational Research, Fourth Edition*, Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.
- www.languageinindia.com
- www.wikipedia.com
- www.springer.com